

ORGANIZATIONAL-LEGAL, SOCIO-ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF SMALL BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN'S AGRICULTURE

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Annotatsiya. Mamlakatda fermer xo'jaliklarini qishloq xo'jalik mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarishdagi asosiy sub'ekt sifatida shakllantirish bo'yicha amaliy choratadbirlar boshlandi va mulkchilik shaklining o'zgarishining keyingi bosqichi ya'ni xususiy mulk shakliga o'tishni jadallashtirishga qaratildi. agrofimlar va fermer xo'jaliklarni paydo bo'lishini ta'minlab, aholini jamoa va xususiy mulk to'g'risidagi tasavvurlarini shakllantirish, ularni yerga egalik hissini hamda sohada ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirishga xizmatlar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: qishloq xo'jalik mahsulotlari, shirkat, fermer xo'jaligi, dehqon xo'jaligi, Ishchi kuchi, Agrar soha, maydon, aholi bandligi, rivojlantirish, foiz.

Абстрактный. В стране начаты практические мероприятия по формированию фермерских хозяйств как основного субъекта производства сельскохозяйственной продукции, а следующий этап изменения формы собственности ориентирован на ускорение перехода к форме частной собственности. разработаны услуги, обеспечивающие появление агрокомпаний и фермерских хозяйств, формирование у населения представлений об общественной и частной собственности, повышение чувства собственности на землю и эффективности производства на местах.

Ключевые слова: сельскохозяйственная продукция, предприятие, ферма, крестьянское хозяйство, рабочая сила, аграрный сектор, площадь, занятость населения, освоение, процент.

Abstract. In the country, practical measures have been started to form farms as the main subject in the production of agricultural products, and the next stage of the change in the form of ownership is focused on accelerating the transition to the form of private ownership. services have been developed to ensure the emergence of agro-companies and farms, to form the public's perception of community and private property, and to increase their sense of land ownership and production efficiency in the field.

Keywords: agricultural products, company, farm, peasant economy, Labor force, Agrarian sector, area, population employment, development, percentage.

Enter. When Uzbekistan gained its independence in 1991, it chose the path of transition to a market economy, and in this, the path of implementing economic reforms in evolutionary stages. In solving this issue, the formation of private property, which is considered one of the important and main property shares in the market economy, has become an urgent issue of the day.

The main part. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 7, 1993 "On measures to deepen economic reforms in agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan" provided the first major step in changing the form of ownership in agriculture and privatization of state property. According to this Decision, 197 out of 1019 farms were to be converted to other forms of ownership by April 1, 1993, and 503 by January 1, 1994. This, in turn, ensured the emergence of cooperative farms, agro-firms, and farms in place of the state-owned state farms and collective farms, helped to form the imagination of the population about collective and private property, and increased their sense of land ownership and production efficiency in the field.

As a result, the share of the state in the production of agricultural products was gradually replaced by other forms of ownership, and companies, peasant farms, and farms appeared as the main producers of agricultural products. By 1995, 87.1 percent of the total agricultural arable land belonged to the companies, and their share in the total gross agricultural product reached 48.1 percent. It was at this time that farms, which today are considered the main economic entity in the cultivation of agricultural products, began to form. Farms occupied 3.8% of the total cultivated area and provided 2.6% of the total gross agricultural product and 5.4% of employment in the agrarian sector (Table 1).

When analyzing the efficiency of land use of the three economic entities, it can be seen that cooperative farms used 1.8 percent of the land to grow one percent of the total agricultural products, while peasants and farms used 0.2 and 1.5 percent of the land, respectively.

Table 1

General indicators of companies, farmers, and farms in the Republic of Uzbekistan (1995) [1]

<i>N^o</i>	Indicators	Companies	agriculture	farms
1	Share of the total cultivated area	87.1	9.1	3.8

2	Share of agriculture in total gross product %	48.1	49.3	2.6
3	Share of workers in jobs in the agrarian sector	58.6	36	5.4
4	Land use efficiency index	1.8	0.2	1.5
5	Efficiency indicator on the use of labor force	1.2	0.7	2.1

From the point of view of the efficiency of the use of the labor force, at that time farms had a much lower indicator compared to other economic entities, and we can see that they used 2.1 percent of the labor force to grow one percent of agricultural products. One of the main reasons for this is the low level of technical and technological equipment of newly established farms, and people's understanding of private property has not yet been sufficiently formed. In general, the above analysis proves that farms are more efficient than companies. As a result, it was aimed to develop farms and form them as producers of the main agricultural products.

Since 1998, the economic reforms implemented in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan and the measures being implemented to create the legal basis for the development of the agricultural sector in the field have been moved to the next stage. This stage marked the beginning of a period of special importance in ensuring the further strengthening of the legal basis for the development of the farming movement, which is one of the main subjects of production in the field today [2].

In particular, the adoption of the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 30, 1998 "On Agricultural Cooperatives (Company Farms), "On Farming" [3], "On Farming" established agricultural cooperatives (company farms), farmers and peasants. served to establish the legal bases, rights, and obligations of their activities, reorganization, and liquidation, and to ensure the regulation of their interactions with other legal entities and individuals.

As a result, practical measures were started to form farms as the main subject in the production of agricultural products in the country, and the next stage of the change of ownership was focused on accelerating the transition to the form of private ownership. According to the Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 13, 1999 "On the program for deepening market reforms and accelerating socio-economic development in the Khorezm region in 1999-2001", 122 of the 132 collective farms in the region were converted into cooperative farms, of

which 8 were unprofitable and had no future. establishment of 531 farms and 1932 peasant farms based on collective farms was determined.

Also, based on the Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 2000 "On the results of the rehabilitation of agricultural enterprises in 2000 and measures for its organization in 2001", 86 collective farms that have been in rehabilitation since 1999 have been transformed into cooperative farms, as well as in rehabilitation since 1999 The rehabilitation period of 59 collective farms was extended for another year, 3031 farms were established based on 52 cooperative farms.

As a result, it was observed that the share of farmers and farms increased, while the share of cooperative farms decreased in land ownership, production, and employment. In particular, by 2002, the share of companies in the total cultivated area was 60.6% and decreased to 26.5% compared to 1995, while the share of peasant farms increased from 9.1% to 11.4%, and the share of farms increased from 3.8% to 28%. Also, the share of companies in the total gross product decreased by 22.2%, the share of peasant farms increased by 14.8%, and the share of farms by 7.4%.

The mentioned changes ensured that the share of cooperative farms in population employment decreased by 17.7 percent, while the share of farmers and farms increased by 4.3 and 13.4 percent, respectively. If we focus on the efficiency indicators, it can be seen that the efficiency of land use decreased in the company and farms, and remained unchanged in the peasant farms. A positive change in the efficiency of the use of the labor force was observed in farmers and farms, and a decrease was observed in cooperative farms.

Adoption of the cited laws and decisions ensured the formation of farms in our country as the main subject of producing agricultural products. In the scientific research conducted on the development of former farms, the years 1998-2002 are considered a special stage in the development of the field from the point of view of their recognition as a separate entity, creation of legal bases, formation of the field as the main producer of goods, and increasing its position in the implementation of reforms in agriculture [4].

As a result of the reforms implemented during this period, the number of farms increased by 25 times compared to 1990-1991 and reached 50,000. Also, the average land area covered by each farmer was increased from 10 hectares to 20 hectares.

The last stage in changing the organizational and legal form of producers in the agrarian sector, starting from 2003, focused on the transfer of cooperative farms to full-

scale farms, the introduction of farmers, and peasant farms as the main producers of agricultural products [5].

Summary. In the implementation of this stage, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the most important directions of deepening reforms in agriculture" of March 24, 2003, No. focus is on implementation, expansion of the independence of agricultural producers, and ensuring their reliable legal protection. According to the decree, preservation of the organizational and legal forms of company, farmer and peasant farms, and development of farms that will become the main agricultural product producer in the future, has been defined as a priority direction.

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